

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

EFFECTS OF BIOGAS SLURRY APPLICATION ON WHEAT YIELD AND QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

Wheat is called "world grain", its yield and quality are closely related to the national economy and people's livelihood. Many studies have shown that fertilizer has the greatest effect on wheat yield and quality among many cultivation factors. Biogas slurry is a brown and bright liquid formed after the fermentation of organic matter. It is a kind of high-quality organic liquid fertilizer with comprehensive nutrients, slow fertilizer efficiency and good utilization value in improving the yield and quality of wheat. This paper reviewed the effect of biogas slurry application on wheat yield and quality, in order to provide basis for promoting wheat growth and improving wheat quality, and promote the application of ecological circular agriculture mode combining agriculture and animal husbandry.

Keywords: Wheat; Biogas slurry; yield and quality; Growth and development.

Biogas slurry is a brown and bright liquid formed after fermentation of organic substances. It contains a considerable amount of nutrient elements such as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, medium elements such as calcium and magnesium, trace nutrients such as iron, copper, zinc and manganese, as well as heavy metals such as mercury, cadmium, chromium, arsenic and lead [1-4]. Not only contains 17 kinds of amino acids, active enzyme, also contain carbohydrates, nucleic acids, vitamins, proteins, hormones, antibiotics, and enzyme hydrolysis, organic acid, humic acid, auxin, gibberellin, vitamins, cytokinins and some antibiotics and other bioactive substances, most of these nutrients exist in the form of available nutrients. Biogas slurry is an effective compound fertilizer with high utilization rate of nutrients and can be quickly absorbed and utilized by crops. In the process of biogas slurry fermentation, the content of indoleacetic acid increases, and the appropriate concentration of auxin can not only promote the development of plant roots, but also contribute to nitrogen metabolism in plants [5]. In agricultural production practice, biogas slurry can not only partially replace chemical fertilizers, but also play a role in the prevention and control of diseases and insect pests, to a certain extent, it can reduce the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides and promote the green development of agriculture [6-8].

Wheat, known as "world grain", is cultivated and consumed in almost every country of the world's five continents. The area and yield of wheat in the world have been the first among cereals for a long time. The

yield and quality of wheat are closely related to the national economy and people's livelihood. Many studies have shown that wheat quality is not only affected by genetic factors, but also by wheat growing environment and cultivation factors. Fertilizer has the greatest effect on wheat yield and quality among many cultivation factors.

At present, many researchers have paid attention to the application of biogas slurry to wheat and carried out research, this paper reviewed the effect of biogas slurry application on wheat yield and quality, in order to provide basis for promoting wheat growth and improving wheat quality, and promote the application of ecological circular agriculture mode combining agriculture and animal husbandry.

1. Effects of biogas slurry application on wheat growth and development

Biogas slurry is rich in minerals and can provide mineral elements needed for plant growth. Short-term application of biogas slurry has a positive impact on soil microorganisms and nitrogen supply [9]. Biogas slurry contains plant hormones that can promote crop growth. Biogas fertilizer had certain effect on wheat plant height in production. The chlorophyll content could be increased with different application amount, indicating that biogas fertilizer could promote chlorophyll synthesis, but the increase rate was different. In terms of wheat growth period, the grain filling stage was the highest, followed by jointing stage and seedling stage. It can also effectively improve photosynthetic rate, leaf water use efficiency and yield [10]. Li Youqiang et al.[11]showed that applying biogas slurry

as base fertilizer could increase the plant height, tiller number and tiller percentage of wheat with an increase of 0.68%-2.77% with the increase of biogas slurry application amount, SPAD value and leaf area index increased correspondingly, and SPAD value and leaf area index before flowering were significantly higher than those of the control.

With the increase of biogas slurry replacement application amount, tiller number and panicle number per plant both showed a trend of gradual increase, while ear-setting rate per plant showed a trend of first increase and then decrease, and 50% biogas slurry application amount reached the maximum value [12]. Biogas slurry application can make leaves dark green in color, and chlorophyll content in leaves tends to increase with the increase of biogas slurry application [13]. However, if the application amount of biogas slurry exceeds a certain amount, wheat maturity will be delayed [12-13].

2. Effects of biogas slurry application on wheat yield

Application of biogas slurry can increase wheat yield by 12.4%-20.7%, and significantly increase spike number and 1000-grain weight per unit area of wheat [10]. The reason is that the late effect of biogas slurry delayed leaf senescence, prolonged the function period of green leaf, and had a good promotion effect on yield.

Li Youqiang et al. [11] showed that biogas slurry as base fertilizer and topdressing fertilizer could significantly increase wheat yield by 3.40%-6.53%, due to the increase of panicle number (2.80%-11.25%) and grain number per panicle (1.90%-2.61%). Most treatments increased the 1000-grain weight, only the lowest dosage of biogas slurry was lower than the control. Xun Zhang [14] conducted a field experiment for 5 years under wheat-rice rotation, containing 2 treatments with equivalent total N usage, CF (Full chemical N fertilizers application) and BS-C (Using pig manure biogas slurry instead of chemical N fertilizer), the result showed that the wheat yield under BS-C increased by 34.9% compared to CF. This is consistent with the research results of Yifan Tang et al. [15]. The increase in wheat yield might be attributed to the significant effect of nitrogen on growth and yield attributes, viz. plant height, effective tillers/m², spikes/m row length, spike length, grains/spike and 1,000 grain weight, which led to increased grain yield significantly [16].

3. Effects of biogas slurry application on wheat quality

Wheat quality indexes are quite different, and wheat protein components are relatively concentrated as evaluation indexes. The study of Feng Wei et al. [17] showed that with the increase of biogas slurry dosage, protein components such as albumin and globulin, gliadin, glutenin content and total protein were improved. Suitable biogas slurry application is beneficial to the improvement of wheat flour quality parameters, good toughness of dough, high strength of gluten and good processing properties of dough. If the application amount of biogas slurry is too large, the protein content and silty parameters of wheat grains will be reduced. Compared with those of the CK, BS treatment not only improved the yield of winter wheat, but also increased

the contents of crude protein and starch in wheat grains [18].

Wang Guiliang et al. [12] used wheat dough stabilization time, wet gluten content, settlement value and protein content as indicators to study the effect of biogas slurry application on wheat quality. The results showed that biogas slurry improved wheat quality indicators to varying degrees, and showed a gradually rising trend with the increase of biogas slurry application amount. Gao Wei et al. [19] believed that the combined application of biogas slurry and chemical fertilizer could promote the improvement of wheat plant trace elements and improve grain quality.

4. Mechanism of improving crop yield and quality by biogas slurry

Biogas slurry is rich in nutrients, which contributes to the dissolution of insoluble nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium elements in soil, improves soil enzyme activity, and enhances the efficiency and permanence of organic fertilizer in soil [20-22]. Biogas slurry can increase nitrogen application, increase tiller rate, enlarge leaf area and prolong photosynthetic time of wheat. At the same time, keep green leaves and delay death etc. [23].

As a high-quality organic fertilizer with both speed and slow, biogas slurry can meet the exogenous substances required for normal crop production, improve crop growth parameters, coordinate the coupling between nitrogen supply capacity and crop demand, and balance carbon and nitrogen metabolism process. Biogas slurry also contains organic acids, antibiotics, hormones, microorganisms, enzymes and other nutrients, which enhance crop stress resistance and promote crop growth [24], increase crop yield and improve product quality [25].

5. Conclusions

To sum up, biogas slurry is a good quick-acting liquid fertilizer, which can not only improve crop yield and quality, meet the needs of pollution-free production, but also reduce pollution, effectively reduce production costs and increase farmers' income, it should be popularized and applied in wheat production.

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